

NEED FOR IDENTIFICATION OF POLLEN GRAINS

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ABSTRACT

The need for identification of pollen grains are the focus of this study. Pollen is tangled directly or indirectly in our daily lives, but few people are aware of this due to their size. We can find pollen everywhere in our house, especially during the flowering season, but we can't tell its pollen with our naked eyes. Pollen grains are invisible to those who are unaware of their existence. Pollen can be found in everything from the air to the food we eat, as well as in science and religious beliefs. Pollen identification is crucial in forensic science, allergy research, geology, geography, climatology, medicine, sanctify, food, and climatology, among other fields. Pollen identification aids in the investigation of numerous criminal cases, the testing of honey quality, the age of sediments, ancient people's food habits, beliefs, allergy causes, climatic conditions of a location, the location of oil mining, the study of fossils, the discovery of historical vegetation changes, insect-eating and migratory habits, cosmetics and medicine, and many more.

INTRODUCTION

Many plant species are still unknown to mankind due to the vastness of the plant world. Plants have two ways of reproducing: sexually and asexually. Sexual reproduction is guided by pollen grains and pollination is the process by which pollen produced by the anther is transferred to the stigma. Cheiropterophily, entomophily, ornithophily, animophily, and hydrophily are examples of biotic and abiotic pollination agencies. The pollen grain is a male gametophyte that is essential for plants but is so small that we can't see it with our naked eyes, so it is produced in large quantities. Shapes, size, exine structure, pollen tube germination, pollinating agencies, pollen dormancy, and other factors can all be

used to differentiate or classify pollen grains. Palynology is a term coined by Hyde and Williams in 1955 to describe the study of pollen grain identification (**Halbritter, et al 2018**).

Camerarius was the first to discover that seed dust is important for seed development in 1694. Carl Nilsson Linnaeus coined the term pollen in 1750. Malpighi discusses the germination furrow, Gleditsch demonstrates the role of pollen in double fertilization, Kolreuter and Spergel discuss the importance of insects in pollination and pollen in sex determination, and Candolle and Spergel discovered pores and furrows in the outer pollen wall. Purkinje's nomenclature system is well-known as a solution to classification-related confusion (Wodehouse, 1937). In 1823, Brown describes the origin and function of the pollen tube. Goppert and Ehrenberg were the first to investigate fossil pollen grains. Fritzsche coined the terms exine, intine, and sporopollenin in 1837, and Nawaschin discovered the callose wall in pollen in 1898. Schacht was the first to notice the pollen's anatomical structure. Reinsch published the first photomicrograph of fossil pollen in 1884 (**Halbritter, et al 2018**).

The shape, size, polarity, aperture, and pollen wall are all aspects of pollen morphology. Pollen's polarity refers to its tetrad orientation. The pollen is isopolar or heteropolar depending on the position of the proximal and distal phases. Fischer's and Garside's laws govern the arrangement of apertures in pollen walls. Pollen size ranges from 5 to 200 micrometres (Rahl, 2008). Pollen from maize plants is the largest, while pollen from forget-me-not plants is the smallest. Pollen can be circular, ovate, triangular spheroidal, cup-shaped, boat-shaped, cube-shaped, tetrahedral, triangular dipyramidal, hexafoil dipyramidal, triangular prism, pentagonal prism, or hexagonal prism shape, etc. The polarity of an aperture determines its terminology. The term "inaperturate" refers to a pollen grain that lacks an aperture. If pollen is present equatorially or globally, it is called porus; if pollen is present distally, it is called ulcus. If pollen is found equatorially or globally, it is called colpus; if pollen is found distally, it is called the sulcus. Poroid is a circular or elliptical aperture with indistinct margins. Exine and intine are two layers found in pollen grains. sporopollenin makes up the outer exine layer, which is divided into sexine and nexine. Cellulose is the main component of intine.

Pollination is an important part of plant life. It is a pollinator-assisted process in which pollen grains are transferred from the anther to the stigma. Based on pollination, plants are classified as cross-pollinated or self-pollinated. Self-pollination causes inbreeding depression and produces offspring with undesirable recessive traits. Self-pollination occurs when flowers are closed or when pollinators are limited. Cross-pollination, on the other hand, produces offspring with high heterosis or hybrid vigour. Pollination is accompanied by pollinators, which are biotic and abiotic factors or agents. Wind and water are examples of abiotic factors. Insects, birds, and animals are examples of biotic factors. Cheiropetrophily refers to bat pollination. Entomophily refers to the study of insects such as beetles, bees, flies, wasps, and moths. Pollination by beetles is called Cantharophily, pollination by bees is called Melittophily, and pollination by flies is called Myophily in entomophily. Hummingbirds and sunbirds

serve as pollinators in the process known as ornithophily. Pollination by abiotic factors such as wind and water is referred to as animophily and hydrophily, respectively.

Because pollen grains are so small, we can't see them with our naked eyes and must use a microscope to identify them. The detailed image of a pollen grain can be obtained using an electron microscope. Observing these images, many techniques are used to identify the characteristic features of a pollen grain. Morphological, hybrid, and texture-based approaches are used in most of these techniques. We can't assess the pollen grain's importance without first identifying it. To make pollen grain research easier and more interesting in the future, and to discover its applications, the first step must be to identify it.

2. Need for Pollen Identification

As we know, pollen is present everywhere in our surroundings. The question is why we need to identify pollen when it is almost non-existent for the majority of people on the planet. Most people just treat their existence like air. But these microspores are able to cause unexpected appearances in our daily lives without our awareness. Who knows, these microspores could be the source of your constant sneezing, skin rashes, burning sensation in your eyes, or throat pain. It is clinically proved in much research that pollen causes allergy in human beings. Pollen also plays an important role in forensic science. In some cases, it helped the forensic doctors in the identification of the actual culprit and crime scene. In geography, pollen helps in the identification of the origin of different plant taxa and the origin of soil. Pollen remains on sedimentary rocks can help in identifying their origin and age. Pollen in charcoal can be evidence of typical fire in geological literature for thousands of years. Pollen helps in understanding the configuration of oil or gas in oil industries. Fossil pollen can help in getting any information related to previous climates and vegetation. Fossil pollen also helps us to construct an idea of ancient life. Pollen and nectar are collected by bees, so the honey they produce in their hives has some amount of pollen in it, which helps in knowing the quality of the honey produced. Although pollen are very small spores, they contain vitamins, amino acids, and carbohydrates that can be used in pharmaceutical and cosmetic industries. Some places in the world where all the sacred activities are still in existence have pollen as their inseparable ingredient. Pollen dust is considered sacred and used in many religious ceremonies.

2.1 Pollen allergy

The development of respiratory symptoms (rhinoconjunctivitis and/or asthma) as a result of inhaling pollen or spores is known as pollinosis, seasonal allergic rhinitis, pollen allergy, or hay fever (Taketomi, et al 2006); (Bartra, et al 2009). The first person to link pollen to allergy was Charles Harrison Blackley (Taylor and Walker, 1973). Pollen allergy is the broadest criterion that necessitates pollen identification research. Pollen grains cause hypersensitivity reactions, which is a major research topic all over the

world (Sushamaraj, 2018). Pollen allergy could be linked to and/or responsible for changes in plant food allergies, as well as esophageal, gastric, intestinal, and digestive inflammation. Pollen and/or spore are thought to be the source of allergens that cause primary sensitization, which is then followed by secondary allergy to plant food containing the same allergen via a cross-reactivity mechanism (Bartra, et al 2009).

According to the WHO (World Health Organization), allergic rhinitis affects 400 million people worldwide, while asthma affects 300 million (Bousquet and Kaltaev, 2007]. In India, allergic rhinitis affects 20% to 30% of the population, and bronchial asthma affects 15% of the population (Heinzerling, et al. 2013). Acute runny nose (rhinorrhoea), chronically inflamed and blocked nose, itching, watery eyes, sneezing, mucus secretion, oedema (fluid retention), itching, prickling, heat sensation, chest tightening, tracheal, and faucal (throat) irritation are all symptoms of allergic rhinitis (Davies, 2019) (Ramchandaran and Aronson, 2011).

In 1919 the search for the allergic factor which causes allergic asthma starts and leads to the discovery of class five Immunoglobulin (IgE) in 1967 (**Johansson, 2016**). The human immune system responds to pollen allergens in two phases. The early phase occurs within 15 minutes and causes sneezing, mucus secretion, oedema, nasal blockage, etc. The later phase occurs after 4-6 hours and it increases the reaction of early phase symptoms (**IgE in Clinical Allergy and Allergy Diagnosis, 2003**).

Skin Prick Test is the diagnostic allergy test it involves pricking in the volar surface of the forearm with the help of a lancet (Frati et al., 2018). In-vitro tests for specific IgE antibodies and Radioallergosorbent tests (RAST) are also performed for detection of allergen-specific IgE antibodies (**IgE in Clinical Allergy and Allergy Diagnosis. 2003**).

John Bostock was the first physician who relates pollen with allergy in 1819 (Ramchandaran and Aronson, 2011). Bostock identifies himself as the patient J.B. (46 years old) who suffer reddening of the eye, discharge of thick mucus fluid and tears, itching, prickling sensation, inflammation, and sensation of heat and fullness around the edges of the lid and inner angle after some time can be felt over the whole eyeball every year in the beginning or middle of June since he was 8 years old. The patient show some more symptoms like chest tightening, sneezing, tracheal and faucal irritation along difficulty in breathing. The patient shows no sign of relief even after a series of treatments unless he confined himself to the house. Susan Gordan (Gordon, 2008) collect air samples and use Polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) filters to quantify exposure to airborne animal allergens. At first, this technique was described by Agarwal and co-workers in 1981. Airborne allergens are present in very low concentrations under normal conditions. Utilizing a pump air along with aeroallergen is drawn through a filtration medium. Very little information is available regarding the intensity of exposure to allergens. The number of allergy patients is directly related to the pollen count during the season (Singh

et al., 2017). Allergic rhinitis symptoms during the early flowering season are more severe than a late flowering season at similar grass pollen concentrations (De Weger et al., 2011).

Respiratory Allergy and Immunology Clinic, Medical College, Thiruvananthapuram compare the study of Intradermal Skin Test results of 1000 registered patients of which 45.87% were male of age group 10 to 49 years. Three pollen grains elicited significant skin test positive in male patients, and those with a history of asthma had the highest level of sensitivity. The results of the study show that allergic reactions are unaffected by the patient's family history and have a substantial impact on the skin test positivity (Sushamaraj, 2018). The antigen from *Cocos nucifera* had the highest rate of total and substantial reaction. The reaction to skin testing was nearly equal for the other two antigens. In many regions of the world, grass pollen is the leading cause of Pollinosis (Freidhoff et al., 1986).

IgE specific for group 1 allergens is found in up to 95% of patients, while group 5 allergens are found in up to 80% of patients who are sensitive to grass pollen, these two groups constitute the major grass pollen allergens (Valenta, et al., 1992).

According to studies, urbanization, high levels of vehicle emissions, and a westernized lifestyle are linked to an increase in the frequency of pollen-induced respiratory allergy, and people who live in cities are more affected by pollen-induced respiratory allergy than those who live in rural areas. And the reason behind this is air pollution and climate change which contain harmful gases like NO₂, O₃, etc. Pollen grains can interact with pollutants in the air, causing a rapid increase in the release of antigens with altered allergenicity (D'Amato et al., 2007).

Fungal spores penetrate the human respiratory tract and cause allergy, and the source of fungal spores is indoor as well outdoor. Indoor sources may be water sources, building materials, and biocontrol (Fungi used for pest control indoors) (Burge, 2002).

A total of 648 patients with pollinosis were included in a study of PFAS (Pollen-food allergy syndrome) in Korea among them 41.7% of the participants show PFAS. Other than oropharyngeal symptoms, 43% of PFAS patients had cutaneous, 20.0% had respiratory, 3.7% had cardiovascular, 8.9% had anaphylaxis, and 4.8% had neurologic problems. Research shows that some food are related to PFAS like Peach (48.5%), kiwi (30.4%), plum (16.3%), chestnut (14.8%), pineapple (13.7%), Pear (8.2%), walnut (14.1%), Korean melon (12.6%), apple (46.7%), tomato (11.9%), peanut (17.4%), apricot (10.7%), ginseng (8.2%), soy (7.4%), carrot (6.3%), banana (5.6%), mango (5.6%), strawberry (4.1%), eggplant (2.6%), orange (1.9%), sweet potato (1.5%), chili (1.1%), wheat (1.1%), almond (1.1%), and lotus root (2.6%) (Kim et al., 2018).

2.2 Pollen in Forensic Science

Forensic science can be used to investigate and prosecute crimes such as rape, murder, and drug trafficking, as well as civil wrongs, such as wilful contamination of air or water or inflicting industrial injuries (Siegel, 2002). Pollen grains are also used in a variety of criminal and civil cases for justice. It involves the identification of pollen, fungal spores, and plant spores collected from the clothes, hairs ([More](#) and [Subir](#), 2015) (Wiltshire, 2006), mud, shoes, nails, and other articles, that can help in resolving many crimes like, rape, murder, terrorism, forgery, homicide, bombing, arson, theft, drug trafficking, counterfeiting, hit and run, assault, poaching, etc (Kumari, et al., 2017). Pollen grains can stay in the intestine for up to 21 days, which makes pollen analysis an important forensic research tool (Arguelles et al., 2015). Forensic experts use the pollen to relate a suspect to the crime scene, relate an item left at the crime scene, relate an item found at the discovery scene to the item found at the crime scene, prove or disprove suspect's alibis, short-list the list of suspects, analyze the route history of various things, such as food and pharmaceuticals, provide geographic information of the source of items, determine the season or year in which an incident occurred, discover hidden graves and human remains, determine a victim's perimortem fate, and analyze the deposition period of human remains (Mildenhall et al., 2006) (Bock and Norris, 2016). Pollen characteristics that make it a piece of crucial evidence from the aspect of forensic science are (Bock and Norris, 2016), their invisibility to naked eye hence easily overlooked by the criminals, b) resistance to degradation, c) their structural uniqueness, d) specific habitat e) predictable pollen pattern throughout the year for each location. Despite the benefits, its use in forensics has not gotten a lot of support from law enforcement and the judiciary for a number of reasons. The reasons may be, Inappropriate or contaminated sample collection, ignorance about the knowledge of palynology among investigators, lawyers, and judges, lack of trained palynologists, lack of liability, lack of access to suitable microscopic and photographic equipment, lack of reference material, lack of funding, and no training facility for pollen forensics study (Bock and Norris, 2016) (Bryant and Jones, 2006). In the United States, forensic palynology has been utilized sparingly. A pollen reference collection for 20,000 species of plants is currently housed at Texas A&M University, which is a US hub for forensic pollen studies. Today, New Zealand can be considered the world leader in forensic palynology (Bryant and Jones, 2006). In 1959, pollen was used for the first time in the investigation of a homicide case in Sweden and Austria (Mildenhall et al., 2006) (Walsh and Horrocks, 2008). Pollen was found to be isolated from animal fur, human hair, clothing, painted wood, rope used to bind a victim, imported medications, and plants (Mildenhall, 2006). Pollen isolated from the paper and ink are very useful in solving a document fraud case (Morgan et al., 2013). Pollen found on a victim's clothing or hair at a graveyard could reveal the time of year the person was murdered (Bryant and Jones, 2006) (Wiltshire and Black, 2006). By observing the pollen linked with the corpse and the seasonal rhythm of pollen release can be used to determine when a buried individual died. Pollen can also be found in the skull of the corpse (Wiltshire and Black, 2006), soil that has been stuck to a suspect's clothing or shoes,

as well as in their automobiles (Mildenhall, et al., 2006). Pollen analysis from soil has been helpful in the investigation of mass graves linked to war crimes. When bodies are retrieved and reburied, the pollen pattern or pollen print in the soil associated with the body may differ significantly from the soil at the new burial site, and these pollen print may help in analyzing the season and/or time of year or place of the crime (Brown, 2006).

2.3 Pollen in Geography

Pollen percentages do not accurately reflect the abundance of related plant species in the vegetation surrounding the pollen sample site due to variances in pollen generation and distribution among taxa (Prentice et al., 2008). One of the most prevalent methodologies for reconstructing previous vegetation and climate is pollen analysis (Quamar et al., 2017). Dust typically contains a variety of other taxa, including a large number of microbial taxa (Brodie et al., 2006), and there is some evidence that analyzing the pollen of these taxa can be used to determine the geographic origin of dust or soil samples (Araujo et al., 2009) (Giampaoli, et al. 2014).

2.4 Pollen in Geology

Geology is the branch of science that deals with the solid Earth. Mineralogy, geodesy, and stratigraphy are among the studies covered (Windley and Harbaugh, 2021). Pollen has been found in relation to charcoal and other evidence of typical fires in the geological literature for thousands, or millions of years (Morales-Molino et al .,2011) (Sniderman and Haberle, 2011). Palynological assemblages are found in almost all sedimentary rock sequences. Palynological fossils' phyla and genera can be used to determine the order of epochs during larger time intervals. Most age assessments for shorter time intervals must be based on assemblages and relative abundance of species. Paleocological criteria differ from neocological criteria in that fossil assemblages represent only a fraction of one or more life communities. The flora and fauna of the lower latitudes have remained relatively stable over long periods of geological time. During warm periods, these biotas expanded into higher latitudes, and during cooler periods, they retreated. Fossil spores, pollen, and cuticles from the land can reveal the age and environment of the continent (Wilson, 1961).

Palynology is a stratigraphic tool used in the oil industry to study rocks deposited in continental, coastal, and shallow-marine environments (Valenti, 2002). To understand the configuration of oil and/or gas bearing-beds within the basin, oil industries conduct pollen analysis (Hopping, 1967).

2.5 Pollen in Climatology

Fossil pollen is used by climatologists to reconstruct former climates (Bock and Norris, 2016). Pollen grains can easily preserved in continental sediments, allowing researchers to learn more about historical vegetational changes and the climatic variations that accompanied them. Because the vegetation is

influenced by climatic circumstances, changes in both qualitative and quantitative parameters of pollen reflect environmental and climatic changes through time (Bajpai, 2017).

2.6 Pollen in Paleontology

Paleontology is the study of fossils that leads us to the understanding of ancient life. Using the indicator species approach, the qualitative characteristics of the landscape are implied from pollen percentage data (Iversen, 1944). Pollen influx data (pollen accumulation rates) are used to create an independent index of plant taxa representation of the vegetation (Hicks and Hyvärinen, 1999). Pollen analysis helps in reconstructing past terrestrial vegetation that combines stratigraphic principles with observations of actual (modern) pollen-vegetation relationships to reveal evidence of past ecological and climate changes (Kneller, 2009). Geologists have successfully used fossil pollen to define oil and gas deposits and, as a result, to use these data to discover new sources (Bock and Norris, 2016).

2.7 Pollen in food (especially honey)

Vitamin content in pollen is higher than beef, cauliflower, tomatoes, eggs, potatoes, with a high concentration of pantothenic acid. In summer, nicotinic acid content reach near to beef and beef liver, and more than yeast and wheat bran, which is higher than that of peas and dried beans. The ascorbic acid content in pollen is comparable to that in endive, canned tomatoes, fresh lettuce, and cooked potatoes. The riboflavin content of pollen is comparable to skimmed milk (Linskens, and Jorde, 1997). Bee products are consist of many components that are required for the proper functioning of basic life processes (Bobis et al., 2010). Honey, pollen, and extracts derived from it, such as propolis, bee bread, bee venom, and royal jelly, are among the bee products. Pollen is frequently referred to as "the best food product on the planet" (Bobis et al., 2010). The world's pollen production is estimated to be around 1500 tonnes per year, with China, Australia, and Argentina producing the most (Estevinho et al., 2011).

Pollen found on or in an insect is identified to establish the insect's eating and migratory habits (Lingren et al., 1993). Pollen grains were used as evidence to find out the source of honey in the United States in the 1970s (Bryant and Jones, 2006). Pollen and nectar are collected by bees, and the honey produced in their hives contains pollen from the flowers they visited (Bock and Norris, 2016). Back in the U.S., even a case was also solved by analyzing the pollen present in honey produced by the honey bees (Bryant and Jones, 2006). Since 1895, it was proved that the geographical origin of honey could be determined by identifying the pollen within the honey (Lieux, 1969). Honey is the only sweetener that may be stored and consumed exactly as produced in nature, without refining or processing (White, 1978). For honeybee, pollen are the main source of proteins and nectar is the main source of carbohydrates (**Jones and Jones, 2001**).

2.8 Pollen in Pharmaceutical

Pollen, like other plant material, has a low content of vitamins E and D but a high content of vitamin B 12, which is one of the reasons for its use as a pharmaceutical preparation (Tull, 1987). Compounds in bee pollen inhibit the growth of Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria, with activity varies depending on the potential of compounds present in each product (Fatrcová-Šramková, et al. 2013). Some pollen internal material is FDA-approved and sold as a homeopathic medicine in hormonal treatments such as Femal and Prostat. The inert and protein-free external wall, known as exine, has the potential to be used in medicine as a drug delivery vector, or an empty carrier into which an active drug can be loaded (Diego-Taboada, et al. 2007). Hemsley et al., demonstrated that a drug could be encapsulated within a mineral capsule and then released slowly when the spore mimic was immersed in simulated gastric fluid. It has been proven that sporopollenin has UV screening and antioxidant properties to some extent. These properties would be extremely beneficial, as encapsulating easily oxidized pharmaceutical actives in sporopollenin would greatly extend their shelf life (Diego-Taboada et al., 2007).

2.9 Pollen in cosmetics

According to recent studies, Wrinkles, senile plaques, and dry skin have all been linked to protein imbalances in the body (Campos et al., 2008). The use of protein from bee pollen in cosmetics has a lot of potentials to fight these problems. Because pollen contains 10.4% essential amino acids like methionine, lysine, threonine, histidine, leucine, isoleucine, valine, phenylalanine, and tryptophan, it has attracted interest for cosmetic purposes. Bee pollen carbohydrates are primarily used as thickeners, protective colloids, emulsion stabilizers, moisturizing, gelling, and chelating agents. Anti-oxidant, anti-viral, anti-cellulite, anti-inflammatory, and anti-aging properties are all present in them. It can be used to prevent the aging of the skin as well as cutaneous disorders. Bee pollen lipids are essential ingredients because they assist to form the permeability barrier that prevents water and electrolytes from passing through the stratum corneum, the outermost layer of the epidermis in the skin (Xi, et al. 2018).

2.10 Sacred pollen

Pollen played an important role in religious ceremonies among many American Indian tribes, and cattail pollen, also known as "Hoddentin" or "Hadentin," meaning "cattail powder," was one of the most important contents of the Apache medicine bundle. Apache throws away the hoddentin to the sun whenever they go to fight, hunt, and/ or plant. It was also given to the sick people as a remedy, and apache sprinkles it over the corpse. Apache worships the sun, moon, and planets by sprinkling the hoddentin (Bourke, 1892). To the Navajo, corn pollen is an inseparable part of their culture. They kept the pollen in pouches and every pouch is for a different purpose like corn pollen pouches for animals and humans are different. Pouches for animals are used to bless a hunt and in hunting ceremonies, as

well as to keep their sheep, cows, and horses healthy (Capelin, 2009). "Yiauhtli," or ragweed pollen, used by the Aztecs (part of today's Mexico), was sprinkled on the faces of captives who were to be sacrificed. Pollen cake was offered to the war-god Huitsilopochtli, while ragweed pollen was given to the Aztecs' divine king Moctezuma. At the summer solstice, women on Minorca are said to have smeared pollen on their faces in an attempt to reclaim their lost youth (Newman, 1984).

1. Discussion

Pollen has been the subject of numerous studies in the past and recent years. Even though pollen is very small and cannot be seen with the naked eye, it is extremely useful in many aspects of life. Many studies have been conducted to better understand the significance of pollen grain.

In India, there are two pollen seasons: tree pollen season from February to April and grass pollen season from September to December (Shah and Pawankar, 2009). *Prosopis juliflora*, *Ricinus communis*, *Morus*, *Mallotus*, *Alnus*, *Quercus*, *Cedrus*, *Argemone*, *Amaranthus*, *Chenopodium*, *Holoptelea*, *Brassica*, *Cocos*, *Cannabis*, *Parthenium*, *Cassia*, and grasses are all allergenically important pollens (Singh and Kumar, 2003). The lowest concentration of grass pollen (10-50 grains/m³) in the air is capable of inducing hay fever symptoms in allergy patients in London (Davies and Smith, 1973). In Cardiff (Wales), 10 grains/m³ (grass pollen) are capable of developing pollinosis symptoms in 10% of patients, and again 50 grains/m³ (grass pollen) are enough to induced symptoms in pollinosis patients in London (Hyde, 1972). When the pollen count was above 37 grains/m³ (grass-pollen) in Bilbao (Spain), 100% of pollinosis patients reported allergic symptoms (Antépara et al., 1995). A count of fewer than 30 grains/m³ (grass-pollen) was shown to be substantially linked with nasal symptoms at the start of the grass pollen season in Turku, Finland (Rantio-Lehtimäki et al., 1991). In northern Europe, Birch is the major pollen allergen-producing tree (Eriksson et al., 1982) (Eriksson, and Holmen, 1996). From April to June, the pollen season is at its peak. As a result of improved diagnostic procedures and changes in farming practices, the frequency of olive-induced pollinosis is improving (Liccardi et al., 1996). The eco-environment and crop management can induce allergological changes, in different varieties of the olive tree (Conde Herna'ndez, et al. 2002). In contrast to bronchial asthma, *Olea europaea* pollinosis is characterized by rhinoconjunctival symptomatology (Liccardi et al., 1996).

During the winter season, Cupressaceae pollen represents at least 30% of the total pollen count in the city of Cordoba, southern Spain (Ruiz de Clavijo, et al 1988), it accounts for 20–40% of yearly pollen rain in Italy and Albania (Mandrioli, et al. 2000) (Priftanji et al., 2000). Cupressaceae pollen has been identified as a source of rising pollinosis in Mediterranean countries like France (Charpin, 2000) (Calleja and Farrera, 2003), Israel (Geller-Bernstein et al., 2000), Spain, and Italy (Italian Association of Aerobiology, 2002) in recent decades, and is responsible for winter pollinosis, which occurs when no other allergenic plants are blossoming (Caramiello et al., 1991). New sources of aeroallergens

emerged as a result of the increased usage of attractive plants in parks and gardens, public and work areas, and private residences (D'Amato et al., 2007).

Hypersensitivity symptoms such as diarrhea, urticaria, rhino-conjunctivitis, and asthma can be triggered by certain food (Eriksson et al., 1982). After eating apple hazelnut, patients with springtime hayfever frequently report itching and tingling in the lips, tongue, and throat, as well as sneezing (**Juhlin-Dannfelt, 1948**). People allergic to birch pollen showed a positive skin reaction to fresh extract of several fruits and vegetables (**Hannuksela, and Lahti, 1977**).

In 1959 a case related to the disappearance of an Austrian man while on a trip down to the Danube River was the first criminal case ever solved by the analysis and identification of pollen found in the mud in the suspect's house (Mildenhall et al., 2006) (Walsh and Horrocks, 2008). In the early 1970s somewhere near the state of Pennsylvania a honey producer accuses the owner of a lima bean farm of using harmful pesticides which cause his bees to fall ill. This case was settled by forensic honey palynology, and the result says that the produced honey does not contain any lima bean pollen means the pesticides used by the farm owner didn't cause any damage to the health of bees (Bryant and Jones, 2006). In New Zealand, a series of cases happen to be solved by using pollen identification, like, a rape and murder case in which the pollen of tree fern and pine was happened to be found on both suspect and victim, a case in which pollen found on the article found at the crime scene tells the occupation of the criminal, a case in which pollen on the dead body didn't match with the local pollen hence it conclude that the body had been shifted from the actual crime scene (Mildenhall, 1990). In NE Bosnia, The United Nations International Criminal Tribunal for the former Yugoslavia (ICTY) investigate the exhumation of mass graves, which happens to be last from 1997 to 2002, also use pollen from the sample of soil present on the corps and conform the exhumation (Brown, 2006).

According to Wilson, the following factors will greatly improve the utility of palynology as a stratigraphic tool: 1) A better understanding of palynological fossils' natural affinities. 2) The importance of species composition and relative abundance in palynological assemblages. 3) Comparison of palynological and associated megafossil assemblages. 4) Utilization of sedimentation study data for environmental and historical purposes. 5) Analysis of fossil biotas and associated sedimentary facies using statistical techniques (Wilson, 1961).

The Mio-Pliocene lacustrine sediments at the Gray Fossil Site in Tennessee, USA, were studied to determine the Late Neogene floral characteristics of a site within the southern Appalachian Mountains (Ochoa et al., 2012). Based on pollen and spore assemblages ranging in age from Albian to Maastrichtian, a palynological investigation of 164 samples from 18 water wells in northern Kordofan, Sudan, identified five informal zones (Schrank, 1994).

Anthropologists can deduce the diets of ancient peoples from pollen grains associated with tools used for food preparation or from pollen grains present in preserved feces (Bock and Norris, 2016). Art appraisers have used pollen to authenticate old paintings (Bock and Norris, 2016). Pollen has been discovered as an artistic medium by modern artists such as Wolfgang Laib, who was born in 1950 (Newman, 1984). Maack, a German inventor, claimed that sporopollenin, a compound found in the unicellular alga *Chlorella vulgaris*, could be used to create solutions with UV protection, anti-wrinkle properties, and other cosmetic benefits (Bourke, 1892).

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